

A Comprehensive Bibliometric Analysis of the Publications of the Journal Library Herald, spanning from 2015 to 2020

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Abstract

The article presents a comprehensive bibliometric study encompassing a six-year analysis of the double-blind peer-reviewed scholarly research journal, Library Herald, spanning from 2015 to 2020. The data, sourced from all issues published during this period, focuses on the final output of research scholars and professionals featured in Volumes 53 to 58. The study scrutinizes the chronological distribution of contributors, the topographical distribution of authors, the most prolific institutions, the most prolific contributors, authorship patterns, and the pattern of citations. The findings indicate that, out of 233 papers, the majority, specifically 126 (54.31%), reflect a single-author contributions pattern. The impact of citing sources in academic writing is crucial. 72.2% of papers did not receive any citations. Only 233 out of 374 papers received citations, emphasizing the importance of citing sources for visibility and validity. 33 articles garnered the most frequent citations, with 66 citations each, while 7 papers received 48 citations. These findings underscore the significance of proper citation in academic work.

Keywords: Library herald, Bibliometric analysis, Topographical Distribution.

1. Introduction

Bibliometrics is a crucial area of study in LIS Field. Research publications are the means of expressing intellectual thought and conveying innovative ideas or information to advance a subject or discipline. Bibliometric analysis, which explores the relationships between information documents and activities which is conducted by librarians and statisticians, as noted by Kumar (2014). This analysis can be carried out at various levels, such as countries, institutions, authors, and journals. The peer-reviewed, double-blind, scientific publication. Library Herald is published by “Delhi Library Association”. It has been published since 1958 and is one of the primeval journals in India that focuses on Library and Information Science. Vellaichmay & Jeyshankar (2015) “stated that in this context, the bibliometric analysis of papers published in Library Herald during the period of 2015-2020, would be useful to reveal the latest publication trend, citation details, major contributing organizations, countries' contribution and most contributing institutions. Further, the analysis would provide useful guidelines for journal editors, librarians, researchers, information scientists and others involved in economic, social and research policy formulation.”

2. Review of Literature

Over the last few years, numerous bibliometric studies have been carried out by contributors, research scholars, and students. We must delve into each of these studies in detail.

Singh and Kumar (2021) carried a study on Bibliometric Study of DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology (2010-2019). The study indicated that maximum number i.e. 258 (47.60%) articles are double authored, followed by single author 172 (31.73%) articles. Garg, Lamba and Singh (2020) conducted a bibliometric analysis of papers published during 1992-2019 in the DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology. According to this study, the most prolific author, B.M. Gupta (CSIR-NISTADS) topped the list while B. R. Babu (University of Madras, Chennai) had the highest value of Citations of Paper (CPP) and Relative Citation Impact (RCI). Patil and Lihitkar analysed 1,005 articles published in 55 volumes (1958-2014) of the Library Herald published by the Delhi Library Association, India. The study found that more than three-fourths of the articles were single-authored and about half of the contributors were by librarians working in universities, colleges, and other institutes. Singh and Bebi (2014) conducted a bibliometric study of the journal Library Herald during the period of study (2003-2012) and resolved that in the study particular journal 234 articles were published, 114 (48.72%) articles were contributed by single authors followed by two authors 90.

The most productive author is Nosrat Riahinia contributed 16 articles, followed by K. P. Singh 08 articles, during the period of study. Verma, Devi and Brahma (2017) conducted a bibliometric study of the DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology (DJLIT) from the marked period (2005-2016) in which 553 articles were published in the particular journal. And analyze various bibliometric pattern such as authorship pattern, most productive author, references distribution pattern, geographical distribution and the state-wise contribution of articles, and found that in the authorship pattern maximum articles contributed by two authors with (41.41%), followed by a single author with (36.88%) and (15.18%) contributed by three authors. M. Gupta was the most productive author with (17.98%) articles contribution, followed by Chennupati K. Ramaiah (9.35%) and S. M. Dhawan (7.19%). New Delhi (23.44%) emerged in first position with the highest number of Contributions, followed by Karnataka (12.75%). The present study is in continuation of the earlier studies on the Library Herald carried out by Riahinia (2009) who did a citation study on Library Herald from the period 2003-2007, Thanuskodi (2011) research work on Library Herald Journal: A bibliometric study, Library Herald Journal: A bibliometric Study conducted by Kumar (2014) and the study conducted by Singh (2014) on Library Herald: A Bibliometric Study (2003-2012).

3. Objectives of the study

This main objective of the study is to analyse the growth in design of papers published from 2015-2020 in the Library Herald Journal. For this purpose following objectives we chosen.

- Analyse article distribution for Indian states and foreign countries based on their topography.
- Find the most relevant and innovative institutions and authors.
- Analyse and research the authorship and citation indexing of the articles.

4. Methodology

A comprehensive analysis was conducted on the website of a highly regarded journal spanning six years from 2015 to 2020. The investigation involved a meticulous examination of crucial data, including author names, publication years, and citations. The research aimed to scrutinize the works of scholarly individuals and professionals whose final publications were featured in the Library Herald, focusing on Volumes 53 to 58. A total of 232 papers were reviewed during the study.

5. Data Analysis and Result

We will obtain important and precise findings by analyzing data through our bibliometric analysis of the article. The following parameters have been thoroughly explained:

5.1 Chronemically Distribution of Contributions

According to Table-1, the years 2017 and 2018 saw the highest number of published articles, totaling 44. Volume 54 in 2016, on the other hand, had the lowest number of papers. It's important to note that the no. of papers published in 2015, 2017, and 2018 surpasses the average no. of papers published from 2015 to 2020, which stands at 38.6% per volume.

Table - 1: Chronemically Distribution of Contributions

S.N.	Year	Volume	Number of Papers	Percentage (%)
1	2020	58	37	15.95
2	2019	57	34	14.65
3	2018	56	44	18.97
4	2017	55	44	18.97
5	2016	54	33	14.22
6	2015	53	40	17.24
Total			232	100.0

5.2 Topographical Distribution of Contributions

The papers published in the Library Herald journal are presented in Table 2 between 2015 and 2020. It is noteworthy that 10 many nations made contributions to the total of 374 articles published. The majority of these contributions came from India, with a total of 331 articles (88.5%). Iran followed with 25 articles (6.7%) contributed. Considering that the journal is published in India, it is understandable why India had the highest number of contributions. It is also worth mentioning that Canada, Italy, Spain, and the UK each contributed only one article (0.3%).

Table - 2: Topographical Distribution of Contributions

S. N.	Topographical Distribution in India and Abroad	Total Number of Publication	Percentage (%)
1	India	331	88.5
2	Iran	25	6.7
3	Saudi Arabia	5	1.3
4	Nepal	4	1.1
5	Nigeria	3	0.8
6	USA	2	0.5
7	Canada	1	0.3
8	Italy	1	0.3
9	Spain	1	0.3
10	UK	1	0.3
Total		374 *	100
<i>* Output is inflated using the complete count approach. Therefore, the publishing is more than just the raw data.</i>			

5.3 Production by Indian States and Union Territories Distributed

The table 3 shows that Union territories and 14 Indian states contributed a total of 331 articles from 2015 to 2020. Delhi was the top contributor with 149 articles (45%), followed by Maharashtra with 30 articles (9.1%) and Karnataka with 20 articles (6.0%). Gujarat and Uttar Pradesh each contributed 13 articles (3.9%). Jammu & Kashmir and Punjab each contributed 7 articles (2.1%).

Table - 3: Production by Indian States and Union Territories Distributed

S. N.	Indian States	Number of Publications	Percentage (%)
1	Assam	5	1.5
2	Delhi	149	45.0
3	Gujarat	13	3.9
4	Haryana	5	1.5
5	Jammu & Kashmir	7	2.1
6	Karnataka	20	6.0
7	Kerala	17	5.1
8	Maharashtra	30	9.1
9	Mizoram	6	1.8
10	Odisha	6	1.8
11	Punjab	7	2.1
12	Telangana/Andhra Pradesh	8	2.4
13	Uttar Pradesh	13	3.9
14	West Bengal	16	4.8

	Total	302	97.2
15	*Other 9 states....	29	8.8
	Grand Total	331	100

Note:1. As “Telangana” split off from “Andhra Pradesh” the two states came together as one.
2. “Himachal Pradesh” “Meghalaya” “Pondicherry” and “Tamil Nadu” (3 each), “Bihar” “Madhya Pradesh” “Rajasthan” and “Uttarakhand” (4 each), and “Tripura” (1).

5.4 Most Prolific Institutions

Research output has been received from 374 institutions, domestic and international. The Delhi University has made a contribution. The highest number of articles, with 45 (12%) articles, followed by “Kharazmi University” in Iran with 17 (4.5%) papers. IGNOU in New Delhi and TISS in Mumbai have contributed 12 (3.2%) articles each, according to the table. Cochin University of Science and Technology in Kerala and CSIR-NISCAIR in New Delhi each contributed 10 (2.7%) publications.

Table - 4: Most Prolific Institutions

S.N.	Name of the institutions	Total Number of Publications	Percentage (%)
1	Banaras Hindu University, UP	4	1.1
2	Banasthali University, Rajasthan	4	1.1
3	Central University of Gujarat, Gujarat	5	1.3
4	Cochin University of Science and Tech., Kerala	10	2.7
5	*CSIR-NISTADS, New Delhi	4	1.1
6	*CSIR-NISCAIR, New Delhi	10	2.7
7	Delhi Library Association, New Delhi	8	2.1
8	Gulbarga University, Karnataka	6	1.6
9	Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar	5	1.3
10	IAFAU, Saudi Arabia	4	1.1
11	*IIT Kharagpur, West Bengal	4	1.1
12	*IIT Delhi, New Delhi	6	1.6
13	IGNOU, New Delhi	12	3.2
14	Kharazmi University, Iran	17	4.5
15	Mizoram University, Mizoram	5	1.3
16	SBUMSc, Iran	4	1.1
17	TISSc, Mumbai	12	3.2
18	University of Delhi, Delhi	45	12.0
19	Visva-Bharati University, West Bengal	4	1.1
	Total	169	45.2
	Other 156 institutions	205	54.8
	Grand Total	*374	100.0

5.5 Most Prolific Authors

A total of 474 writers contributed papers between 2015 and 2020. The distribution of paper contributions is shown in Table 5. Less than three articles were provided by 303 (81.0%) of the writers. Nine authors each supplied three (0.8%) publications, compared to three authors who each gave four (1.1%) pieces. K.P. Singh from the University of Delhi made the most contributions with 14 (3.7%) publications, followed by K.C. Garg from CSIR-NISTADS, New Delhi, with 7 (1.9%) papers.

Table - 5: Most Prolific Authors

S.N.	Author	Institution	Number of Publications	Percentage (%)
1	Chadha, R.K.	Parliament of India, New Delhi	3	0.8
2	Garg, K.C.	CSIR-NISTADS, New Delhi	7	1.9
3	Khanchandani, Vanita	Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, New Delhi	3	0.8
4	Kumar, Shailendra	University of Delhi, Delhi	4	1.1
5	Riahinia, Nosrat	Kharazmi University, Iran	4	1.1
6	Salimi, Zahra	Kharazmi University, Iran	3	0.8
7	Satiya, M.P.	Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar	3	0.8
8	Sen, B.K.	Bibliometrics Expert Committee, Department of Science and Technology, Government of India	6	1.6
9	Sharma, R.K.	Delhi Library Association, Delhi	3	0.8
10	Shukla, Archana	Indira Gandhi National Open University, New Delhi	3	0.8
11	Singh, K.P.	University of Delhi, Delhi	14	3.7
12	Singh, Rajesh	University of Delhi, Delhi	5	1.3
13	Vashishth, C.P.	Delhi Library Association, New Delhi	3	0.8
14	Verma, M.K.	Mizoram University, Mizoram	3	0.8
15	Yadav, A.K.S.	Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai	3	0.8
16	Zeinali, Vahide	Shahid Beheshti University of Medical Sciences, Iran	4	1.1
	Total		171	19.0
	Other authors contributing papers in the range of 1-2		303	81.0
	Grand Total		474	100

5.6 Authorship Pattern

The table below displays the pattern of authorship in articles published from 2015 to 2020. The majority of papers, 126 or 54.31%, were written by just one author. Two authors contributed to

83 articles, which is 35.78%. The table also indicates that 23 articles, or 9.91%, were created by multiple

Table - 6: Authorship Pattern

S. N.	Year/Volume	Single Author	Two Authors	Multi Authors	Total
1	2020 (58)	26	8	3	37
2	2019 (57)	11	21	2	34
3	2018 (56)	20	17	7	44
4	2017 (55)	33	10	1	44
5	2016 (54)	12	15	6	33
6	2015 (53)	24	12	4	40
Total (%)		126 (54.31)	83 (35.78)	23 (9.91)	232(100)

5.7 Format of Citations

When writing, it's important to give credit to sources that have influenced your work. This is done through citations, which briefly reference the source within the text and provide a corresponding entry in the references section of the work. By acknowledging the relevance of other works to your topic, you demonstrate the depth of your research and the credibility of your arguments. The impact of a citation can be measured by how many times it's been cited by other articles. For instance, a recent study found that out of 374 papers published in the *Library Herald* between 2015 and 2020, only 233 received citations. The majority of papers, 72.2%, did not receive any citations. However, 33 articles stood out as the most frequently cited, with 66 citations, while 7 papers received 48 citations. These numbers highlight the importance of citing sources in academic writing and its possible effects. It can have on the visibility and validity of your work.

Table - 7: Format of Citations

S. N.	Citations	Articles	Total no. of Citations
1	1	44 (11.8)	44
2	2	33 (8.8)	66
3	3	7 (1.9)	21
4	4	11 (2.9)	44
5	5	2 (0.5)	10
6	6-8	7 (1.9)	48
Uncited		270 (72.2)	0
Total		374 (100)	233

5.8 Highly Cited Papers

Eight works have acquired four or more citations after their publication, according to the table below. India-based writers contributed to seven providing the last contribution. Two of the eight

Publications are from the "Karnataka" region, and there is also one each from West Bengal, Kerala, Mumbai, and Saudi Arabia.

Table - 8: Highly Cited Papers

S. N.	Bibliographic Details	Affiliation	Citations
1	Sanjeeva, M. & *Powdwal, S. Library Herald, 55(4), 2017, 467-487	VES College of Arts Science and Commerce, Maharashtra & *SNDT Women's University, Maharashtra	8
2	Koley, S., & *Sen, B.K. Library Herald, 54(2), 2016, 174-190	Durgapur Institute of Advanced Technology & Management, West Bengal & *Bibliometrics Expert Committee, Dept. Sc. & Tech., Government of India	7
3	Parameshwar, S., *Goutamib & **Patil, D.B. Library Herald, 54(3), 2016, 315-330	Gulbarga University, Karnataka, *City Central Library, Karnataka, & **Gulbarga University, Karnataka	6
4	Velmurugan, V.S., & *Amudha, G. Library Herald, 53(2), 2015, 121-141	Kalasalingam University, Tamil Nadu & *VHNSN College, Tamil Nadu	5
5	Biradar, B.S., & Kumar, D.V. Library Herald, 53(2), 2015, 107-120	Kuvempu University, Karnataka	4
6	Sudhier, K.G., & *Anitha, C.K. Library Herald, 53(2), 2015, 152-167	University of Kerala, Kerala & *Sree Buddha College of Engineering for Women, Kerala	4
7	Yadav, A.K.S., & Vohra, Niharika Library Herald, 54(1), 2016, 64-81	Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai	4
8	Waris, A., Ahmad, S., Isam, C., Abdel-Magid, M., & * Hussain, A. Library Herald, 55(3), 2017, 339-351	Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University, Saudi Arabia & *King Saud University, Saudi Arabia"	4

6. Conclusion

The Library Herald is a journal that showcases innovative and creative research in the study of information science and libraries. An analysis of the journals' publications during the dynamic period of 2015 to 2020 revealed that the highest number of papers was published between 2017 to 2018, totalling 44. Among the countries that contributed to the journal, India had the highest Number of published articles, with a total of 331. Notably, the union territory of Delhi had the highest number of publications in India, with a total of 149 (45%). During this period, the University of Delhi was the most prolific institution, contributing 45 papers. The journal features 126 single authors, 83 double authors, and 23 multi-authors who all have made valuable contribution. Citing sources in academic writing is crucial for validating research and increasing visibility. With 72.2% of papers not receiving any citations, the impact of proper citation practices becomes evident. Out of 374 papers, only 233 received citations, emphasizing the significance of citing sources. Additionally, 33 articles garnered the most frequent citations, with

66 citations each, while 7 papers received 48 citations, underscoring the critical importance of meticulous citation in academic work.

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